

The Sundarbans, the World's Largest Tidal Halophytic Mangrove Forest: Its Economic and Ecological Significance

M. S. Zaman^{1,2}, Tabina H. Chowdhury³

¹Department of Biological Sciences, Alcorn State University, Lorman, MS 39096

²Department of Biology, South Texas College, McAllen, TX 78501

³Edmond Memorial Highschool, Edmond, OK 73013

*Correspondence: M. S. Zaman

Emails: zaman@alcorn.edu, mzaman@southtexascollege.edu

Received: 6/14/2024 / Accepted: 7/7/2024

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12683069>

Abstract

The Sundarbans, located along the southwestern coast of Bangladesh and southeastern India, is a remarkable ecosystem characterized by extensive mangrove forests, marshlands, and waterways, spreading across approximately 10,000 square kilometers. This vast area is recognized as the world's largest tidal halophytic mangrove forest, known for its ability to thrive in warm, humid climates and its unique assortment of salt-resistant plant life. The Sundarbans mangroves are essential for the livelihoods of coastal communities, supporting fishing industries and offering resources like timber, fuel woods, honey, and medicinal plants. Moreover, the mangroves play a crucial role in coastal protection, shielding against cyclones, storm surges, tidal waves, and erosion. Additionally, the mangroves serve essential ecological functions, including carbon sequestration, and providing habitats for various plant and animal species. Despite the pivotal functions, the mangroves face significant threats from human activities, notably pollution, land use changes, and the impacts of climate change. The escalating demand for resources has led to extensive deforestation resulting in habitat degradation and a reduction in the Sundarbans' size. This review delves into the economic and ecological features of the Sundarbans, examining its landscapes, biodiversity, and the obstacles posed by resource exploitation, and climate change, while also considering potential strategies for mitigation.

Keywords: Sundarbans, mangrove forest, ecological and economic significance, climate change

Citation: Zaman, M.S., Chowdhury T.H. 2024, *The Sundarbans, the World's Largest Tidal Halophytic Mangrove Forest: Its Economic and Ecological Significance*, *Bangla J. Interdisciplinary Sci.*, 2 (1): E1-E15.

Note: In this article, the term "Sundarbans" is used in both singular and plural forms. The plural form ("Sundarbans") refers to the forest, while the singular form ("Sundarbans") denotes the region.

Introduction

Along the southwestern coast of Bangladesh and the southeastern coast of India lies the *Sundarbans*, one of the world's most intriguing and unique ecosystems (Figure 1). This vast expanse of mangrove forests, marshlands, and waterways form the world's largest tidal halophytic mangrove forest. Mangrove forests flourish in the warm, humid climates of the tropics and subtropics, constituting a distinct coastal ecosystem. Populated by salt-resistant trees and shrubs, these lush forests are finely adapted to the dynamic environment of coastal wetlands (Mukhopadhyay et al., 2015).

Figure 1: The majestic and magnificent Sundarbans, Bangladesh. (A) An intricate web of forests, rivers, and channels, Credit: Tauhid Biplob, Wikimedia Commons (WC), 2018a; (B) Partially submerged Nipa palm in hightide, Credit: Ferdous, WC, 2014; (C) The mangrove flora, Credit: Syed Sajidul Islam, WC, 2016a.

In addition to fostering a rich array of diverse flora and fauna, mangrove forests offer a multitude of ecosystem services, encompassing carbon sequestration, erosion mitigation, and shielding against storms and natural calamities. Their significance lies in safeguarding coastal lands from erosion, and buffering against waves and currents (Islam et al., 2019). Communities residing along coastlines heavily rely on mangrove resources for sustenance and livelihoods. These forests nurture commercially valuable fish and shellfish species, help sustain local fishing enterprises, and ensure global food security. Additionally, mangrove forests contribute to the local economy by supplying timber, fuel woods, medicinal plants, and assorted resources.

Sundarbans' geography is captivating and crucial to understanding its economic and ecological significance, cultural importance, and the challenges it faces. Its recognition as a *UNESCO World Heritage Site* and a *Ramsar Site* makes the Sundarbans an ecological marvel of global significance.

In 1992, the Bangladeshi portion of the Sundarbans was designated as a Wetland of International Importance under the Ramsar Convention. In 1997, UNESCO selected the Sundarbans in Bangladesh as a World Heritage Site, recognizing its exceptional significance and uniqueness. This includes wildlife sanctuaries covering about 32,400 hectares, which form the core breeding area for several endangered species. UNESCO described the Sundarbans as one of the world's largest remaining areas of mangroves, noting its support for exceptional biodiversity in terrestrial and aquatic environments (Nishat et al., 2019). The Indian part of the Sundarbans was designated a World Heritage Site in 1987 and a Ramsar site in 2019 (Sundarban Wetland, 2019).

Regrettably, the Sundarbans and its delicate ecosystems are under extensive threat from human activities, notably pollution, deforestation, and the impacts of climate change (Saoum and Sarkar, 2024). With a gradual surge in global resource demand, vast strips of land are being cleared for

agricultural purposes, such as rice cultivation, shrimp farming, and other related uses. This extensive land recovery for human usage is a major driver of mangrove deforestation (Islam and Bhuiyan, 2018). Currently, the Sundarbans spreads across approximately 10,000 square kilometers, about 3 percent of the global mangrove forest area (Kanan et al., 2023). However, about 200 years ago, the Sundarbans measured about 16,700 square kilometers (World Heritage Datasheet, 1997), revealing a massive reduction from the previous size.

This review article aims to explore the geographical features of the Sundarbans, delving into its varied landscapes, ecosystem, abundant biodiversity, economic and ecological significance, and the intricate interplay between land and water. Furthermore, it will investigate and highlight the challenges confronting the Sundarbans, particularly deforestation and the misuse of resources by humans, while also examining potential mitigation strategies.

Geographic Position

The Sundarbans, an extensive mangrove region, is located in the delta formed by the confluence of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna rivers as they empty into the Bay of Bengal. The formation of the forest commenced geologically as soil erosion from the Himalayas transported sediment downstream, depositing a mixture of sand, clay, silt, and salt (Raha, 2005). This world's largest mangrove forest is situated at coordinates 21°30'-22°30'N and 89°00'-89°55'E (Rahman et al., 2015). The Sundarbans stretches across Bangladesh and into the Indian state of West Bengal. About 62 percent (6200 km²) of the forest is in Bangladesh, and the remaining 38 percent (3800 km²) is in India (Ghosh et al., 2015) (Figure 2).

Figure 2: The map of the Sundarbans, Credit: Nirvik 12, WC, 2015.

The Ecosystems

The Sundarbans is characterized by its intricate network of waterways, mudflats, and islands, shaped by the confluence of the Ganges, Brahmaputra, and Meghna rivers. This dynamic deltaic region undergoes constant transformation due to the flow of high and low tides, which persistently shape its ever-changing landscape.

The Sundarbans experience a highly humid tropical monsoon climate, characterized by an annual rainfall of 1,920 mm and temperatures mostly ranging from 21°C to 30°C. The monsoon season typically spans May to October (Rahman et al., 2009). The Baleswar, Passur, Raimangal, and

Sibsha are among the major rivers serving as the primary sources of freshwater. The tides in the Sundarbans follow a semi-diurnal cycle, featuring two high tides and two low tides each day (Bandyopadhyay, 2019). The region is divided into three main zones: the tidal waterways, the mangrove forest, and the hinterland.

Tidal Waterways

The Sundarbans are crisscrossed by an extensive network of tidal waterways, including rivers, creeks, and channels, which serve as lifelines for the region. These waterways are influenced by the daily flow of high and low tides, creating a unique ecosystem where freshwater from the rivers mixes with saltwater from the Bay of Bengal. Tidal fluctuations also play a vital role in shaping the sedimentation patterns and nutrient distribution within the Sundarbans, supporting its rich biodiversity.

Mangrove Forest

The Sundarbans mangroves are characterized by dense distributions of salt-tolerant trees and shrubs adapted to the brackish waters of the delta. The Sundarbans harbor numerous species of mangroves, which serve as a natural barrier against coastal erosion, protect inland areas from storm surges and cyclones, and offer essential habitats for diverse flora and fauna.

Hinterland

Beyond the mangrove forest, the Sundarbans extends into the hinterlands (surroundings), comprising low-lying islands, mudflats, and salt marshes. These hinterland areas are characterized by their dynamic nature, constantly shaped by the deposition of sediment carried by the rivers and tides. Despite the challenging conditions, these areas support vast wildlife, including numerous mammals, reptiles, and bird species.

Flora

At the core of the Sundarbans is the distinctive mangrove flora, adapted to thrive in the intertidal zone. These resilient plants withstand the persistent low and high tides, maintaining a delicate balance between the saline waters of the Bay of Bengal and the freshwater rivers that nourish them. In an early study, 334 plant species were recorded in the Sundarbans (Prain, 1903). Recent studies reported 230 floral species (Siddiqui, 2016) and 528 species of vascular plants (Rahman, et al., 2015) in the habitat. The dominating woody plants in the Sundarbans include the Sundari (*Heritiera fomes*), Gewa (*Excoecaria agallocha*), Goran (*Ceriops decandra*), Passur (*Xylocarpus mekongensis*), Keora (*Sonneratia apetala*), and khalshi (*Aegiceras corniculatum*) (Rahman, 2000).

The magnificent Sundari (Figure 3A), appropriately named after the Sundarbans itself, stands tall with its unique pneumatophores rising above the waterline, facilitating gas exchange in the anaerobic soils. Its timber, valued for its durability, has been exploited over the years, highlighting the delicate balance between human needs and conservation efforts. The Gewa (Figure 3B), with its extensive roots dipping into the brackish waters, provides refuge and nesting sites for countless bird species. Meanwhile, the Goran, which grows as a small tree or shrub, with its complex root system, acts as a barricade against coastal erosion, shielding the hinterland from the fury of cyclones and tidal surges.

Figure 3: (A) The Sundari, Credit: Sarangib, WC, 2016b; (B) Gewa trees, Credit: Vengolis, W.C. 2013.

Besides these woody plant species, the Sundarbans harbor a plethora of halophytic plants, including the nipa palm (*Nypa fruticans*), commonly called “golpata”; the mangrove date palm (*Phoenix paludose*), commonly called “hetal”; the tiger fern (*Acrostichum aureum*), and the saltwater-loving shrub, the kankra (*Bruguiera gymnorhiza*), each playing a vital role in sustaining the ecosystem's complex web of life.

Fauna

The Sundarbans abound with life, hosting approximately 50 species of mammals, 50 species of reptiles, 8 species of amphibians, 400 species of fish, and 320 species of birds, including migratory species (Acharja, 2024). Beneath the green canopy of mangroves, a vibrant fauna thrives, each species uniquely adapted to the challenges presented by this complex habitat and intricately intertwined in the complex web of predator and prey. Among them, the iconic Royal Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris*) (Figure 4A) remains a supreme predator, representing the spirit of the Sundarbans that roam its complex lands and waterways. The Sundarbans encompass more than just the habitat of the majestic tiger; it serves as a sanctuary for many other animal species, from the charming Chital deer (*Axis axis*) (Figure 4B), estuarine crocodiles (*Crocodylus porosus*) (Figure 4C), Irrawaddy dolphins (*Orcaella brevirostris*) (Figure 4D), mudskippers (*Periophthalmus* spp.), fishing cats (*Prionailurus viverrinus*) to enormous pythons (*Python molurus*).

Additionally, this mangrove forest serves as a nursery for many fish species. A survey conducted between June 2015 to July 2017 revealed that the Sundarbans are a habitat for 322 fish species (Habib et al., 2020). They help sustain the livelihoods of countless fishermen who depend on these waters.

The Sundarbans are also home to over 300 avian species, including the globally endangered masked finfoot (*Heliopais personata*) and the majestic, white-bellied sea eagle (*Haliaeetus leucogaster*).

Figure 4: (A) The Royal Bengal Tiger, Credit: Charles J. Sharp, WC, 2020a; (B) Spotted deer, Credit: Charles J. Sharp, WC, 2018b; (C) Estuarine crocodiles, Credit: Bernard Dupont, WC, 2020b; (D) Irrawaddy dolphins, Credit: Dan Koehl, WC, 2011.

Economic Significance

The Sundarbans is a vital economic asset for Bangladesh and India, playing a crucial role in sustaining the economic well-being of the region and supporting the livelihoods of coastal populations. It supports the livelihoods of millions of people through fishing, and harvesting crab, honey, beeswax, fuelwood, timber, medicinal plants, and thatching material (Rahman, 2009). Local communities depend on the resources provided by the forest for their sustenance and economic well-being. A 2018 World Bank document estimated that the economic values of Bangladesh Sundarbans were 0.2 to 356, 0.4, 0.06 to 29, and 0.011 to 19.25 million USD from fisheries, timber, fuelwood, and honey, respectively (The World Bank, 2018). A recent publication reported the estimated annual per-hectare values for various resources in the Bangladeshi region of the Sundarbans as follows: honey at \$41.40, beeswax at \$11.12, timber at \$31.24, fuelwood at \$19.65, thatching materials at \$13.06, fodder at \$23.40, and medicinal plants at \$56.09 (Kanan et al. 2024).

According to a 2020 report by Bangladesh Environment and Development Society, about 3.5 million coastal people depend on the natural resources of the Sundarbans for their livelihoods. However, the region faces substantial social and environmental challenges, including poverty, limited access to land use and safe drinking water, absence of electricity, inadequate housing, compromised health and sanitation services, security issues, and the depletion of biodiversity (Circular Conservation, 2020).

By providing employment opportunities in fishing, forestry, and ecotourism sectors, the forest reduces dependency on vulnerable coastal activities such as agriculture and aquaculture. Moreover, traditional knowledge and practices among local communities passed down through generations help in adapting to cyclonic conditions and minimizing risks during extreme weather events.

Fisheries

Fisheries is one of the primary economic activities supported by the Sundarbans. The intricate network of water channels and estuaries within the mangrove forest provides an ideal breeding ground for numerous species of fish, shrimp, and crabs. Local fishermen heavily rely on these abundant resources for their livelihoods. The Sundarbans contributes substantially to Bangladesh's fish production, meeting both domestic demand and serving as a source of export revenue. In addition to the 2018 World Bank report, as stated earlier, Rahman et al. (2018) suggested that in 2017, the economic valuation of the Sundarbans' fisheries was about 216.71 million USD.

Timber and Non-Timber Forest Products

The Sundarbans mangroves offer timber and non-timber forest products that contribute to the local economy. While sustainable timber harvesting is mostly regulated, the regulation of products such as honey, wax, medicinal plants, and thatching materials is mostly loose as they are collected and traded by local communities. These forest products provide additional income opportunities for marginalized populations living in and around the Sundarbans, contributing to poverty alleviation and rural development efforts. The estimated annual valuations of fuelwood and honey sourced from the World Bank (2018) and Kannan et al. (2024) reports have been mentioned above.

Tourism

The Sundarbans' unique ecosystem, rich biodiversity, and exciting landscapes attract tourists from around the world. Ecotourism has emerged as a significant source of income for local communities and the government. Tourist activities such as wildlife safaris, bird watching, and exploring the mangrove forests generate revenue through entrance fees, guided tours, and hospitality services. Moreover, the Sundarbans' designation as a *UNESCO World Heritage site* and *Ramsar site* enhances its appeal to international tourists, further boosting the tourism sector's contribution to the economy. The estimated annual contribution from Sundarbans tourism to Bangladesh is about 53 million USD (Nobi et al., 2021).

Ecosystem Service Value

Studies indicate that mangrove trees exhibit remarkable efficiency in carbon storage, with an estimated worldwide annual monetary value of \$194,000 per hectare. On a global scale, the collective mangroves across the Earth deliver approximately \$2.7 trillion in services each year (Uijtewaal, 2021). The total ecosystem service values of the entire Sundarbans (Bangladesh and India) were estimated at approximately \$27,450 million, \$26,666 million, and \$24,140 million for the years 1975, 2000, and 2020, respectively. Regrettably, there has been an estimated total loss of ecosystem service value amounting to \$3,311 million between 1975 and 2020 (Bera et al., 2022). Furthermore, as mentioned earlier, the Sundarbans play a crucial role as a barrier against storms, offering substantial economic value by reducing the impacts of climate change. They serve vital functions in coastal protection, such as stabilizing shores, safeguarding agricultural lands, capturing nutrients and sediment, and shielding human settlements and infrastructure from natural disasters like cyclones, storm surges, and tidal waves. Though quantifying the economic value of these ecosystem services is challenging, it demonstrates significant effectiveness in preventing damage and upholding coastal resilience.

Ecological Significance

As the world's largest mangrove forest, the *UNESCO World Heritage site*, and a *Ramsar site*, the Sundarbans is a natural wonder providing invaluable ecosystem services.

Carbon Sequestration and Climate Regulation

The Sundarbans play a vital role in carbon sequestration and climate regulation. Mangrove forests are highly efficient in trapping carbon dioxide from the atmosphere and storing it in their biomass and soil. This helps combat climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions and stabilizing global temperatures. Forests store carbon within both vegetation and soil. Through the process of photosynthesis ($6\text{CO}_2 + 6\text{H}_2\text{O} \rightarrow \text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_6 + 6\text{O}_2$), plants absorb carbon dioxide and convert it into carbohydrates, cellulose, and other forms of organic carbon, which are then stored in various parts of the plant. A significant portion (63-77%) of this above-ground carbon is sequestered in the heartwood. Additionally, approximately 48% of the forest's carbon is contained within the leaf litter and soil (Webber, 2024). A study by the Bangladesh Forest Department conducted between 2009-2010 estimated that 411,639 hectares of forest in the Bangladesh part of the Sundarbans stored 387.7 megatons of carbon dioxide and 105.6 megatons of carbon (BD Forest Dept., 2024).

A 2015 study showed that the amount of carbon stored varied significantly across different vegetation types and salinity zones. Sundari, the dominating plant of the forest, stored the most carbon (360.1 ± 22.71 metric tons of carbon per hectare) as compared to other vegetation. The freshwater zone stored the highest carbon (336.09 ± 14.74 metric tons of carbon per hectare), followed by zones with moderate and high salinity (Rahman et al., 2015). The average carbon storage capacities of the Sundari, Baen, Keora, and Gewa plants, which are the predominant woody species in the Sundarbans, were determined to be 41.3 percent, 40.71 percent, 40.68 percent, and 39.06 percent of their biomass, respectively. Additionally, younger and faster-growing forests exhibited higher annual sequestration rates (Datta et al., 2021).

Safeguarding Coastal Areas as Natural Barrier from Cyclones and Storm Surges

Bangladesh is highly vulnerable to natural disasters, particularly cyclones from the Bay of Bengal. These destructive storms bring strong winds, torrential rains, and storm surges, posing significant threats to lives, property, and livelihoods. In this vulnerability, the Sundarbans provide natural barriers, offering crucial protection to the coastal areas against the fury of cyclones.

Mangroves flourish in saltwater environments, extending their roots along the coastline. Over time, these roots intertwine to form a dense network that captures sediment and creates a physical barricade between the ocean's waves and the shoreline (Newcomb, 2024). The dense mangrove vegetation of the Sundarbans, with its elaborate network of roots and branches, protects the shorelines against storm surges generated by cyclones. The forests absorb and dissipate the energy of incoming waves, thereby reducing the height and intensity of storm surges before they reach the mainland. This protective function helps to minimize coastal erosion, prevent inundation of low-lying areas, and safeguard critical infrastructure and human settlements along the coastline.

Absorption of Wind Energy

During cyclones, the mangroves' extensive canopy cover and dense vegetation play a crucial role in absorbing wind energy. The vast branches of mangrove trees help slow down the cyclonic winds as they pass through the forest. This reduces the impact of strong winds on coastal communities, preventing the destruction of buildings, boats, and other structures. By disintegrating wind energy, the Sundarbans help minimize wind-related damage and loss of lives during such catastrophic events. Over the past two decades, the Sundarbans have faced several significant cyclones, including Sidr in 2007, Aila in 2009, Phailin in 2013, Hudhud in 2014, Fani in 2019, Bulbul in 2019, Amphan in 2020, Yaas in 2021 (Ghosh and Mistri, 2023), and the recently recorded Remal in 2024. The super cyclone Sidr damaged around 40% of the Sundarbans and caused an estimated \$142.9 million in damage (Saadi, 2010; Khan et al., 2021). The impact could have been far more devastating without the Sundarbans' forests acting as a buffer against the force of the winds.

Conservation Value

The Sundarbans represents the largest span of halophytic mangrove forests globally and are located within the WWF (World Wildlife Fund) Global 200 Eco-region. The WWF Global 200 Eco-region project studies global biodiversity to pinpoint certain terrestrial, freshwater, and marine areas rich in biodiversity. These areas serve as key examples of Earth's ecosystems. The wildlife sanctuaries of the Sundarbans and its surrounding areas are collectively recognized as World Heritage sites, and the entire Sundarbans region is designated as a biosphere reserve by UNESCO (Pletcher, 2024).

As stated earlier, the Sundarbans holds the recognition as *Ramsar Wetland* and *UNESCO Biosphere Reserve*. Within this protected area lie the Tiger Reserve, National Park, and the wildlife sanctuaries (World Heritage Datasheet, 1997). These facts testify that the Sundarbans are distinguished for their rich biodiversity, providing home to numerous animal species, notably the endangered iconic Royal Bengal tiger, spotted deer, wild boar, rhesus monkey, an extensive bird population, and many species of fish. Additionally, the region is home to numerous threatened reptiles, such as the Indian python, and estuarine crocodile (UNESCO, 2024).

Being the apex predator, the Royal Bengal tiger plays a vital role in maintaining the ecological balance of the region by controlling the population of herbivores such as deer and wild boar. Additionally, the intricate network of roots in the mangrove ecosystem provides habitat and breeding grounds for various marine and terrestrial species, contributing to biodiversity conservation. The Sundarbans represent important ecological processes, including monsoon rain flooding, delta formation, tidal influence, and plant colonization.

Gradual Degradation of The Sundarbans and Its Impact on Bangladesh

The Sundarbans mangroves are under a barrage of challenges arising from human activities, such as habitat destruction, pollution, sea level rise, and climate change, alongside unsustainable fishing, deforestation, and poaching. These factors are rapidly deteriorating the integrity of the Sundarbans. Poachers target tigers for their valuable body parts, which are sold at high prices in illegal wildlife markets, while other vulnerable species like deer, otters, and crocodiles also fall prey to poaching for their skins, meat, and body parts. This indiscriminate killing disrupts the delicate ecosystem balance, endangering species' survival.

A study using Landsat imagery from 1975 to 2006 showed a net erosion of about 5.9 percent of the forest. Severe tropical cyclones in 1977 and 1988 reduced the mangrove forest by 19.3 percent and damaged around 50 percent of the dense forest. Recovery from such damage took over 25 years. The study also reported that the biodiversity of the Sundarbans depended on freshwater flow, and its future was threatened by climate change. Moreover, climate change could increase the intensity and frequency of severe cyclones and salinity in the water channels (Islam, 2014).

Illegal logging and deforestation for profit, as well as land clearing for agriculture and development, add to the degradation of this delicate ecosystem. The loss of mangrove habitat not only weakens the Sundarbans' capacity to combat climate change and shield coastal regions from natural calamities but also disturbs the habitats of numerous plant and animal species, driving them toward extinction. Urbanization, industrialization, and infrastructure development aggravate habitat destruction, while pollution from industrial waste, oil spills, and solid waste contaminates water bodies and soils, endangering aquatic life and mangrove vegetation. Habitat fragmentation due to road, dam, and settlement construction disrupts wildlife corridors, isolating populations and reducing biodiversity.

These combined threats jeopardize the equilibrium of this fragile ecosystem. Conservation efforts are stalled by various challenges, including poverty, corruption, weak law enforcement, inadequate knowledge and policies, and climate change. For example, the construction of a coal-fed thermal power plant in Rampal, 14 km north of the Sundarbans, has been criticized for violating Ramsar Convention and UNESCO rules for World Heritage Sites, endangering the Sundarbans' biodiversity and ecological values. Furthermore, rising salinity levels in the Sundarbans due to saltwater intrusion from obstructed freshwater flows and sea-level rise pose significant risks. Studies suggest that the freshwater discharge of the Ganges River decreased from 3,700 m³/s in 1962 to 364 m³/s in 2006 due to the construction of the Farakka Barrage by India in 1975 (Islam and Gnauck, 2008).

Such a dramatic reduction in freshwater flow has alarming consequences for the Sundarbans' ecosystem. The ecological consequence of such hydrologic alteration includes the destruction of breeding and rearing habitats for several Gangetic fish, birds, and other animal species (Jahan, et al, 2017), increased salinity in the southwestern coastal region of Bangladesh (home to the Sundarbans), and a reduction in fish and agricultural diversity (Gain and Giupponi, 2014). Overall, this dam has transformed the broader water and riverine ecology of the country. Moreover, the sea level rise near the Sundarbans is reported to be 3.90 ± 0.46 mm per year. The decreasing discharge of the Ganges River and the accelerating sea-level rise near the Sundarbans amplify vulnerability to climate change impacts. Estimates suggest that 40-60 percent of the mangrove area could vanish if sea levels rose by 1 meter. Additionally, the increased frequency of cyclonic storms further threatens the Sundarbans' stability.

Conclusions

Between 2004 and 2022, the Sundarbans experienced an average annual reduction rate of 2.66 percent, primarily due to deforestation and land use changes (Saoum and Sarkar, 2024). The gradual degradation and potential loss of the Sundarbans present a pressing concern due to its critical ecological significance. As one of the most diverse ecosystems globally, it shelters numerous plant and animal species, many of which are unique and endangered. The disappearance of the habitats would lead to the extinction of numerous species, disrupting ecological balance and

reducing genetic diversity. Additionally, the Sundarbans play a vital role in carbon storage, climate regulation, and coastal defense. Without it, the impacts of climate change would worsen, natural calamities would increase in frequency, and coastal regions would be left vulnerable to erosion and flooding. By acting as a carbon sink, the mangrove forests aid in climate stabilization, thereby indirectly mitigating the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events, such as cyclones.

Economically, the Sundarbans are indispensable to Bangladesh. Sectors such as fisheries, tourism, forestry, and agriculture rely heavily on this mangrove ecosystem. If the Sundarbans were to vanish, these sectors would suffer, resulting in the loss of livelihoods for millions of people. Being one of the most climate-vulnerable countries, Bangladesh relies on the Sundarbans as a natural shield against cyclones, storm surges, and sea-level rise. Without it, the risks of coastal erosion, flooding, and salinity intrusion would escalate, leading to population displacement, aggravating social and economic disparities, and magnifying the adverse effects of climate change.

Despite its global recognition, the ecology of this magnificent mangrove forest faces severe threats from unsustainable exploitation and pollution, endangering the ecological integrity and biodiversity of the forests. The exploitation also has significant implications for local communities that rely on forest resources for their livelihoods and sustenance. Indigenous peoples and traditional forest dwellers, who depend on the forest for food, medicine, and shelter, are disproportionately affected by habitat loss and declining forest resources. Moreover, the degradation of ecotourism opportunities due to environmental damage could deprive marginal communities of substitute sources of income, further contributing to poverty and marginalization. As mentioned earlier, conservation efforts face numerous challenges, including weak law enforcement, corruption, poverty, and lack of awareness. Collaboration among conservation organizations, government agencies, and local communities is essential to address these challenges through initiatives, such as increased patrols, community-based conservation programs, public awareness campaigns, and sustainable livelihood projects. Given the scale and complexity of the issue, concerted actions at regional, national, and international levels are necessary to effectively protect the Sundarbans mangroves and their precious biodiversity.

Preserving the Sundarbans is not only crucial for Bangladesh's economic future but also for safeguarding its rich biodiversity and ecological heritage. By recognizing its value and investing in its conservation, Bangladesh can enhance its resilience to cyclones and secure the well-being of its coastal populations for generations to come. Urgent action is needed to halt poaching and destruction, preserve the Sundarbans for future generations, and ensure its survival as an invaluable natural treasure. As a global community, we must recognize the intrinsic value of the Sundarbans and take concerted action to protect and preserve it to benefit all.

Acknowledgements: The authors acknowledge Mr. Rakeen Zaman for his valued assistance with the graphics.

Bibliography

Acharja, A. 2024, Project Sundarbans before it is too late. Daily Observer, URL: <https://www.observerbd.com/news.php?id=460009> (Accessed: 6/29/2024).

Bandyopadhyay, S. 2019, Sundarban: A Review of Evolution & Geomorphology.
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.25774.54084>.

BD Forest Department. 2024, সূন্দরবনে কার্বন জরিপ (The Sundarbans Carbon Inventory). Forest Department, Peoples Republic of Bangladesh, URL: <https://bforest.gov.bd/site/page/6ec068d0-f8ad-4092-8212-39f5bd733c35/-> (Accessed: 6/14/2024).

Bera, B., Bhattacharjee, S., Sengupta, N., Shit, P.K., Adhikary, P.P., Sengupta, D., Saha, S. 2022, Significant reduction of carbon stocks and changes of ecosystem service valuation of Indian Sundarbans. *Nature*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-11716-5> (Accessed 6/13/2024).

Circular Conservation. 2020, Natural, Social and Economic Regeneration in the Sundarbans of Bangladesh, URL: <https://www.circularconversations.com/earth-heroes/bangladesh-environment-and-development-society> (Accessed 6/12/2024).

Datta, A., Rashid, T., Biswas, M. (2021). Sequestration and Storage Capacity of Carbon in the Mangrove Vegetation of Sundarban Forest, Bangladesh. *Int. J. Sci. Eng. Res.* 12. 1098-1101. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14299/ijser.2021.02.04>.

Gain, A.K., Giupponi, C. 2014, Impact of the Farakka Dam on Thresholds of the Hydrologic Flow Regime in the Lower Ganges River Basin (Bangladesh). *Water*, 6: 2501-2518, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/w6082501>

Ghosh, A., Schmidt, S., Fickert, T., Nüsser, M. 2015, The Indian Sundarban Mangrove Forests: History, Utilization, Conservation Strategies and Local Perception. *Diversity*, 7: 149-169.

Ghosh, S., Mistri, B. 2023, Cyclone-induced coastal vulnerability, livelihood challenges and mitigation measures of Matla-Bidya inter-estuarine area, Indian Sundarban. *Nat Hazards (Dordr)*, 116 (3): 3857-3878. DOI: 10.1007/s11069-023-05840-2.

Habib, K.A., Neogi, A.K., Nahar, N., Oh, J., Lee, Y.H., Kim, C.G. 2020, An overview of fishes of the Sundarbans, Bangladesh and their present conservation status. *J. Threatened Taxa* 12(1): 15154-15172, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.11609/jott.4893.11.15.15154-15172>, URL: <https://threatenedtaxa.org/index.php/JoTT/article/view/4893/6634>.

Islam, M.M., Borgqvist, H., Kumar, L. 2019, Monitoring mangrove forest landcover changes in the coastline of Bangladesh from 1976 to 2015. *Geocarto Int.*, 34: 1458-1476, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/10106049.2018.1489423>.

Islam, M.T. 2014, Vegetation Changes of Sundarbans Based on Landsat Imagery Analysis Between 1975 and 2006. *Landscape Environ.*, 8 (1): 1-9, URL: <https://ojs.lib.unideb.hu/landsenv/article/view/2304>.

Islam, S.M.D.U., Bhuiyan, M.A.H. 2018, Sundarbans mangrove forest of Bangladesh: Causes of degradation and sustainable management options. *Environ. Sustain.*, 1: 113-131, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42398-018-0018-y>.

Islam, S.N. and Gnauck, A. 2008, Mangrove Wetland Ecosystems in Ganges-Brahmaputra Delta in Bangladesh. *Front. Earth Sci. China*, 2: 439-448, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11707-008-0049-2>.

Jahan, I., Lee, S.U., Panta, S., Ritchie, K. 2017, Farakka Barrage Action Initiative and Response, University of Delaware, Regional Watershed Management. URL: <https://www.wrc.udel.edu/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/FREE-Farraka-Barrage-Report-2017.pdf> (Accessed: 6/16/2024).

- Kanan, A.H., Pirotti, F., Masiero, M., Rahman, M.M. 2023, Mapping inundation from sea level rise and its interaction with land cover in the Sundarbans mangrove forest. *Clim. Change*, 176: 104.
- Kanan, A.K., Masiero, M., Pirotti, F. 2024, Estimating Economic and Livelihood Values of the World's Largest Mangrove Forest (Sundarbans): A Meta-Analysis. *Forests*, 15: 837, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/f15050837>.
- Khan, S.K., Abdullah, S., Salam, M.A., Mandal, T.R., Hossain, M.R. 2021, Review Assessment of Biodiversity Loss of Sundarban Forest: Highlights on Causes and Impacts. *Ind. J. Forestry Res.*, 8 (1): 85-97. URL: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/1e5b/111546e9bd4f6996ab2e260b13fa2382b0eb.pdf> (Accessed: 6/29/2024).
- Mukhopadhyay, A., Mondal, P., Barik, J., Chowdhury, S.M., Ghosh, T., Hazra, S. 2015, Changes in mangrove species assemblages and future prediction of the Bangladesh Sundarbans using Markov chain model and cellular automata. *Environ. Sci. Process Impacts*, 17: 1111–1117, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c4em00611a>.
- Newcomb, T. 2024, Uh-Oh, the Mangroves Are Rapidly Migrating North. *Popular Mechanics*, URL: <https://www.popularmechanics.com/science/environment/a61414294/why-mangroves-are-rapidly-migrating-north/>
- Nishat, B., Rahman, A.J.M.Z., Mahmud, S. 2019, Landscape Narrative of the Sundarban: Towards Collaborative Management by Bangladesh and India, URL: <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/539771546853079693> (Accessed: 12/7/21).
- Nobi, M.N., Sarker, A.H.M.R., Nath, B., Roskaft, E., Suza, M., Kvinta, P. 2021., Economic valuation of tourism of the Sundarban Mangroves, Bangladesh. *J. Ecol. Nat. Environ.*, 13 (4): 100-109, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5897/JENE2021.0910>.
- Pletcher, K. 2024, Sundarbans. *Britannica*, URL: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Sundarbans> (Accessed: 5/8/24).
- Prain, D. 1903, The flora of Sundarbans. *Records Botanical Survey of India*, 114: 231-272.
- Raha, A.K. 2005, Monitoring Changes in Sundarbans Mangrove Forest using RS/GIS, URL: <http://www.gisdevelopment.net/application/environment/wetland/envwm004.htm> (Accessed: 6/29/2024).
- Rahman, M., Jiang, Y., Irvine, K. 2018, Assessing wetland services for improved development decision-making: a case study of mangroves in coastal Bangladesh. *Wetlands Ecol. Manage.*, 26: 563-580.
- Rahman, L. M. 2000, The Sundarbans: A Unique Wilderness of the World. *USDA Forest Service Proceedings RMRS-P-15-VOL-2*. 143-148, URL: https://www.fs.usda.gov/rm/pubs/rmrs_p015_2/rmrs_p015_2_143_148.pdf (Accessed: 5/9/24).
- Rahman, M. M., Chongling, Y., Islam, K. S., Haoliang, L. (2009). A brief review on pollution and ecotoxicologic effects on Sundarbans mangrove ecosystem in Bangladesh. *Int. J. Environ. Engineering*, 1(4), 369-383.
- Rahman, M.M., Khan, M.N.I., Hoque, A.F., Ahmed, I. 2015, Carbon stock in the Sundarban mangrove forest: Spatial variations in vegetation types and salinity zones. *Wetl. Ecol. Manag.*, 23, 269–283.

- Rahman, M.S., Hossain, G.M., Khan, S.A., Uddin, S.N. 2015, An Annotated Checklist of the Vascular Plants of Sundarban Mangrove Forest of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh J. Plant Taxon.*, 22 (1): 17-41. URL: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/reader/354082c8b997a5927e477e1025e0636f3f47580b> (Accessed: 6/29/2024).
- Saadi MLK (2010) Hurricane Sidr claims beautiful mangroves. URL: <http://www.islamonline.net> (Accessed: 6/29/2024).
- Saoum, M.R., Sarkar, S.K. 2024, Monitoring mangrove forest change and its impacts on the environment. *Ecological Indicators* 159: 111666, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2024.111666>.
- Siddiqui, A. H. 2016, Flora and faunal resources and ecosystem conservation in the Sundarbans. *Int. J. Agric. Inno. Res.*, 5(3): 1473-2319.
- Sundarban Wetland. 2019, Ramsar Sites Information Service, URL: <https://rsis Ramsar.org/ris/2370>.
- The World bank. 2018, Benefits of Cooperation: Focus on the Sundarbans Identification and Assessment, URL: <https://documents1.worldbank.org/curated/zh/384881587110084376/pdf/Benefits-of-Cooperation-Focus-on-the-Sundarban-Identification-and-Assessment-Lead.pdf> (Accessed: 6/12/2024).
- Ujttewaal, I. 2021, World Mangrove Day: The Value of Mangroves for Marine Life, Coastal Communities and Climate Change, Bazaruto Center Scientific Studies, URL: <https://bcssmz.org/the-value-of-mangroves/#:~:text=Because%20of%20the%20incredible%20efficiency,trillion%20in%20services%20every%20year> (Accessed: 6/11/2024).
- UNESCO. 2024, The Sundarbans, URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/798/> (Accessed: 6/12/2024).
- Webber, S. 2024. How do trees store carbon. *Creating Tomorrows Forests*, UK. URL: <https://www.creatingtomorrowforests.co.uk/blog/technical-note-how-do-trees-store-carbon#:~:text=Photosynthesis,convert%20sunlight%20into%20chemical%20energy> (Accessed: 6/23/2024).
- Wikimedia Commons. 2011, Irrawadi Dolphin (Credit: Dan Koehl, CC BY 3.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported license), URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:DKoehl_Irrawaddi_Dolphin_jumping.jpg (Accessed: 6/11/2024).
- Wikimedia Commons. 2013, Gewa Tree (Credit: Vengolis, CC BY-SA 3.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/3.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 Unported), Wikimedia Commons, URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Excoecaria_agallocha.jpg (Accessed: 6/11/2024).
- Wikimedia Commons. 2014, Sundarban (Credit: Ferdous, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license., URL: [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundarban_\(61\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundarban_(61).jpg) (Accessed: 6/11/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2015, Maps of the Sundarbans (Credit: সন্দরবনের মানচিত্র, Nirvik12, Public domain, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license.), Wikimedia Commons, URL:

<https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundarbans-de.svg> (Accessed: 6/11/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2016a, The Sundarban forest river channel, Bangladesh.jpg (Credit: Syed sajidul islam, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license., URL:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundarban_\(61\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundarban_(61).jpg) (Accessed: 6/12/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2016b, Sundari Tree (Credit: Sarangib, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons, made available under the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 Universal Public Domain Dedication, Wikimedia Commons, URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sundari_Tree.JPG (Accessed: 6/10/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2018a, Sundarban U shape river (Credit: Touhid biplob, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license., URL:

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:U_shape_river.jpg (Accessed: 6/10/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2018b, Spotted Deer (Credit: Charles J. Sharp, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license, URL:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Spotted_deer_\(Axis_axis\)_male.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Spotted_deer_(Axis_axis)_male.jpg) (Accessed: 6/14/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2020a, Bengal Tiger (Credit: Charles James Sharp, CC BY-SA 4.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 International license), Wikimedia Commons, URL:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Bengal_tiger_\(Panthera_tigris_tigris\)_female_3_crop.jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Bengal_tiger_(Panthera_tigris_tigris)_female_3_crop.jpg) (Accessed: 6/14/2024).

Wikimedia Commons. 2020b, Saltwater Crocodile (Credit: Bernard DUPONT from FRANCE, CC BY-SA 2.0 <<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/2.0/>>, via Wikimedia Commons, licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 2.0 Generic license), Wikimedia Commons, URL:

[https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Saltwater_Crocodile_\(Crocodylus_porosus\)_\(10106344616\).jpg](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Saltwater_Crocodile_(Crocodylus_porosus)_(10106344616).jpg) (Accessed: 6/14/2024).

World Heritage Datasheet. 1997, The Sundarbans, URL: <http://world-heritage-datasheets.unep-wcmc.org/datasheet/output/site/the-sundarbans/> (Accessed: 5/8/24).